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COMPATIBILITY INDEX FOR DEFECT FREE FORMING WITH DOUBLE CURVATURE

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- Composite aerospace structures production rate increases
- Defect mechanisms frequently introduced with automation
- Automated forming processes currently only controlled through temperature, pressure and tool design
- Limited investigation of effect of stacking sequence on formability

- Theory - Ply deformation principles
- Theory - C_{max} derivation
- Experimental set up
- Results and Discussion
- Conclusions

Theory

Johnson, KJ, Butler, R, Loukaides, EG, Scarth, C & Rhead, AT 2019, 'Stacking sequence selection for defect-free forming of uni-directional ply laminates', *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 171, pp. 34-43.

- Assumption: Linear elastic uncured resin properties
- Minimise energy by maximising deformation in resin-dominated modes i.e. significantly more energy is required to deform fibres
- Ply deformation to act in-plane, rather than out-of-plane (wrinkling/bridging)
- Stiffness matrix derived from Kelvin notation

Theory – eigenmodes of deformation

Voigt notation – classical CLT

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & Q_{16} \\ Q_{12} & Q_{22} & Q_{26} \\ Q_{16} & Q_{26} & Q_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{pmatrix}$$

$[Q_V]$

Kelvin notation

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \sqrt{2}\tau_{xy} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & \sqrt{2}Q_{16} \\ Q_{12} & Q_{22} & \sqrt{2}Q_{26} \\ \sqrt{2}Q_{16} & \sqrt{2}Q_{26} & 2Q_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy}/\sqrt{2} \end{pmatrix}$$

$[Q_K]$

Eigenvalues

Eigenvectors

Theory - Single 0° Ply Deformation

Resin Mode I

Resin Mode II & II*

Fibre Mode

$$[Q_K] = \lambda_1 \begin{bmatrix} v_{1,1} \\ v_{1,2} \\ v_{1,3} \end{bmatrix} [v_{1,1} \quad v_{1,2} \quad v_{1,3}]^T + \lambda_2 \begin{bmatrix} v_{2,1} \\ v_{2,2} \\ v_{2,3} \end{bmatrix} [v_{2,1} \quad v_{2,2} \quad v_{2,3}]^T + \lambda_3 \begin{bmatrix} v_{3,1} \\ v_{3,2} \\ v_{3,3} \end{bmatrix} [v_{3,1} \quad v_{3,2} \quad v_{3,3}]^T$$

Sum of outer products x λ_i stiffnesses

	Resin Mode I			Resin Mode II & II*			Fibre			
λ (kPa)	$v_{1,1}$	$v_{1,2}$	$v_{1,3}$	λ (kPa)	$v_{2,1}$	$v_{2,2}$	$v_{2,3}$	λ (kPa)	$v_{3,1}$	$v_{3,3}$
100	0	1	0	338	0	0	1	1.28×10^8	1	0
					0	0	-1			

Example compatibilities – 2 plies

Ply compatibility given by the vector dot product:

0° Ply

$$[0 \ 1 \ 0] \times \begin{bmatrix} 0.41 \\ 0.41 \\ 0.82 \end{bmatrix} = 0.41$$

-45° Ply

$$[0 \ 1 \ 0] \times \begin{bmatrix} 0.71 \\ -0.71 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = -0.71$$

Interface Angle	Example	Deformation Mode of Adjacent Plies			
		M1/M1	M1/M2	M2/M1	M2/M2
45°	0/-45	0.41	-0.71	0.82	0

Example compatibilities - locking

- Locking detected automatically – central ply cannot deform without resulting in -ve dot product

Compatibility index - C_{max}

Sum of dot products of deformation modes from neighbouring plies across all interfaces

Compatibility value

$$C(i_1, \dots, i_N) = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{j=2}^N [v_{i_{j-1}}]^T [v_{i_j}]$$

Average by total interfaces

energy minimization implies laminate will deform using the most compatible set of modes i.e. maximum $C(i_1, \dots, i_N)$

$$C_{max} = \max_{i_1, \dots, i_N \in I} C(i_1, \dots, i_N)$$

Enumeration and linear integer programming used to find C_{max} ; the latter takes <1s for a 100 ply stack on a standard desktop PC.

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Experiments

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Forming Set-up & Tool Geometry

- Doubly curved tool geometry
- AS4/8552 UD Prepreg
- 24 Ply QI stacks

S. Erland Characterisation of uncured carbon fibre composites, University of Bath, 2016. PhD Thesis.

Forming Set-up & Tool Geometry

Pre-Forming

Post-Forming

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Results

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Results – Low temperature (40°C)

$[(45/-45)_3(0/90)_3]_s$

$C_{max} = 0.91$

$[(45/0/-45/90)_3]_s$

$C_{max} = 0.56$

$[(45/0)_3(-45/90)_3]_s$

$C_{max} = 0.70$

Results – High Temperature

Forming Temperature: **60°C**

QI₁ [(45/-45)₃(0/90)₃]_s

$C_{max} = 0.91$

Forming Temperature: **80°C** (optimum)

QI₂ [(45/0/-45/90)₃]_s

$C_{max} = 0.56$

Results – Slip planes

QI1: $[(45/-45)_3(0/90)_3]_s$

$C_{max} : 0.91$

QI2: $[(45/0/-45/90)_3]_s$

$C_{max} : 0.52$

Block formation & sufficient single ply deformation = **more** formable

No block formation & low single ply deformation = **less** formable

Results – Non – standard and ZD

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QI₁
[(45/-45)₃(0/90)₃]_s
 $C_{max} = 0.91$

QI₄
[(67.5/-22.5)₃(22.5/-67.5)₃]_s
 $C_{max} = 0.91$

QI₂
[(45/0/-45/90)₃]_s
 $C_{max} = 0.56$

QI₅
[(67.5/22.5/-22.5/-67.5)₃]_s
 $C_{max} = 0.56$

ZD₁
[(45/0/-45/0)₃]_s
 $C_{max} = 0.71$

QI₆
[45/-45/45/-45/0/-45/90/45/0/90/90/0]_s
 $C_{max} = 0.82$

Results – Non-standard spiralling

60 degree interface, non-standard QI design

Side view

$$\text{QI}_7$$
$$[(60/0/-60)_4]_s$$
$$C_{max} = 0.60$$

$$\text{QI}_8$$
$$[(90/30/-30)_4]_s$$
$$C_{max} = 0.60$$

60° spiral
similar to
standard
angle 45°
locking
spirals e.g.

45/0/-45
90/45/-45

Note: In the top case the wrinkles are mainly 0 driven, whereas in the bottom the wrinkles are forced in line with the 30 and -30 degree plies (as no 0's are present)

- Stacking sequence effects laminate formability

Adjacent plies with a 90 degree interface angle form with less defects

Locked ply arrangements e.g. 45/0/-45 or 90/45/0 produce defects

- A Compatibility index (C_{max}) has been developed and correlates well with defect severity
- Tailored stacking sequences allow defect free forming at lower temperatures improving rate
- Complex geometries can be formed defect free (at optimal temperatures)
- For small scale low deformation forming, as interface and not ply angle correlates with defects, non-standard angles produce no benefit compared to standard angles.

- Account for tool geometry
- Apply deformation theory to defects generated in AFP/Autoclave consolidation scenarios
- C_{max} for ply drops and woven/NCF materials
- Non-standard angles when tool length and/or high curvature effects forming

Acknowledgements

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